

**Investigating the Drivers of Lavender Market Development in Tehri Garhwal,
Uttarakhand, India**

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Abstract

Due to its growing economic importance and anticipated growth in market demand, Lavender is a hot topic in study in Tehri Garhwal district of Uttarakhand. However, a number of challenges hamper the development of the Lavender sector along with the value chains. Therefore, this paper explores the Lavender value chains timeline from crop to products, examining and comparing the expanding knowledge on the price spread, marketing cost, marketing margin, farmer's share in consumer's rupee and marketing efficiency of Lavender value chains that could lead to new products and uses. The chains are of two times mainly, Farmers – Contractor – Processor – Wholesaler – Retailer – Consumer and Farmers – Contractor – Retailer – Consumer were followed in the sample area. The overall marketing cost was least at in value chain II for Lavender bulbs varied to the extent of ₹32, 45.5 and 43 per kg at pre-, during- and post-pandemic, respectively, mainly due to direct selling of produce to retailers. The marketing margin was lower in value chain II for Lavender bulbs that was ₹2188.8, 3731.7 and 15495 per kg for bulbs at pre-, during- and post-pandemic, respectively due to the less number of intermediaries. The farmer's share in consumer's rupee was relatively high ranging from 9.86 to 13.52 per cent for bulbs, respectively, at pre-, during- and post-pandemic, respectively in value chain II. It was mainly due to direct procurement of raw material of Lavender from farmers to retailers via contractors. Therefore, the outcomes ultimately demonstrated that through the elimination of one or more middlemen and the reduction of marketing expenses, farmers could significantly increase their portion of the rupee paid by the end user. A higher index of marketing efficiency (1.16, 1.15 and 1.11 for bulbs at pre-, during- and post-pandemic, respectively).

Keywords: Value chain, Pandemic, Consumer rupee, Marketing efficiency, Marketing margin, Price spread, Lavender, Marketing cost, Producer share, Marketing intermediaries

Lavender (*Lavandula officinalis*), a fragrant perennial shrub belonging to the *Lavandula* genus within the *Lamiaceae* family, is primarily recognized for its essential oil and can be found growing naturally in the Mediterranean, Russia and Africa. It is cultivated for the production of oil, fresh blossoms, dried items, nourishment and additional applications (Giray, 2018). Its blooms are used to make the essential oil that is used in aromatherapy, baked goods, candles, spreads, massage oils, scents, hair care products, powders, washing bars and herbal infusions. It exhibits a multitude of therapeutic qualities, holds anti-convulsant, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory features. Lavender gets its name from the Latin word *lavare*, which means washing or bathing and has uses in both internal and exterior cleansing and disinfection in addition to its therapeutic properties (Cristea and Boros-Iacob, 2017). According to LisBalchin (2002), cultivars of Lavender began to proliferate in the early 1600s. She also highlighted the challenges associated with designating species, hybrids, and cultivars because the same plant may look very different when grown in various environments. On a global scale, the primary Lavender-producing countries are Bulgaria, France, Russia, Ukraine, Moldova, Romania, Hungary, Poland, Italy, Spain, Turkey, Morocco, the United Kingdom, the United States, Australia, South Africa and China (Crişanet *et al.*, 2023). At present, Bulgaria holds a prominent position in Lavender cultivation (Stanev *et al.*, 2016; Giray 2018; Zagorcheva *et al.*, 2020) with an extensive cultivation area exceeding 11,145 hectares and a production of 50,126 tons in the year 2022 (Anonymous 2022). In the early 20th century, Lavender was first brought to Bulgaria using plant material from France (Kozuharova *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, Cardoz and Chowdhury 2023 (Invest India Website) reported that India is ranked 8th in the world for Lavender production, confirming the evidence. According to the FAO Statistical Yearbook for 2020, 10,000 metric tons of Lavender were produced in India in 2020 and were valued around \$10 million. India, which ranks 7th in the world for Lavender export value, has a significant export potential. India shared 4.51% of the value of Lavender exports in 2022, representing approximately \$104.48 million. Essential oils, which are used in a variety of industries including aromatherapy, cosmetics and fragrance, make up the majority of these exports (Tridge Website).

The quantity of academic studies has grown in tandem with the popularity of Lavender. For instance, a case study carried out in Turkey by Gül *et al.*, 2016 revealed that relative profit was 1.65, average Lavender yield was 1636.70 kg/ha, cost of production for 1 kg of Lavender was \$0.95 and net profit per hectare was \$1018.37, which is quite high when compared to

other agricultural products. Similar economic analysis studies were undertaken in Bosnia and Herzegovina for organic Lavender by **Pecoet *et al.*, 2015**. They estimated the overall profit per hectare to be around \$1237 and the average cost of one kilogram of Maillet oil hybrids to be around \$68, respectively. **Singh *et al.*, 2007**, similarly came to the conclusion that Lavender cultivation was profitable in the Himachal Pradesh district of Chamba and that the sale of Lavender oil may result in substantial farm profits on the assumption that excellent agronomic management techniques were used.

Previous academic studies, which tended to be either local market-focused and/or generally constrained, centered on agricultural study and were far removed from marketing and marketing-related issues. Numerous obstacles restrict the Lavender value chain, which connects growers and consumers. Therefore, the production of Lavender is crucial for the ecosystem and community as a whole, as well as for the farmers who benefit economically from it.

This study analyzes the Lavender value chain in the Tehri Garhwal district in the Garhwal division of Uttarakhand using data gathered from participants in the Lavender value chain (farmer, contractor, processor, wholesaler, retailer and consumer). The report, in more detail, names the participants and describes how they fit into the Lavender value chain. It looks at how market margins are divided up along the supply chain.

Material and Methods

Study area and data collection

The study was carried out in the Tehri Garhwal district, which is found in India's Uttarakhand state's northwest region. The neighbourhood is located between the latitudes of 30°03' and 30°53' N and 77°56' and 79°04' E. The choice of the Garhwal division was deliberate because Uttarakhand still has a strong agricultural economy. The district of Tehri Garhwal was chosen from the division because it had a higher proportion of its land in Lavender cultivation than the hilly regions. The four pattis of the Tehri Garhwal district—Dharkot (Dhar Payakoti) patti, Dung Badiyar patti, Kunjani patti and Saklana patti—were purposefully chosen as the subject of this study because it had never been done before and had not been concentrated in these pattis of the Garhwal division. A sample of 70 farmers (convenient and judgemental sampling), 10 contractors, 3 processors, 3 wholesalers and 5 retailers from the Tehri Garhwal district were chosen in order to achieve this. Customers were also chosen through convenient sampling based on their satisfaction and comments regarding Lavender items.

Consequently, 91 individuals in all were included in the sample survey. To ensure a thorough approach to data collection, well-structured questionnaires/schedules with multiple-choice and open-ended questions, interview schedules and group discussions were used in conjunction with the survey to obtain primary data from the participants. Personal meetings, phone conversations and WhatsApp were used to conduct in-depth interviews with respondents. In addition, several covert conversations with the respondents were held in order to uncover more insights.

Furthermore, secondary information about the state and division was gathered from a number of government organizations, including the CIMAP (Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants), the SMPB (State Medicinal Plant Board) and the CAP (Centre for Aromatic Plants), as well as research reports, journals, newspapers, different books and web portals about Lavender production and marketing practices.

Methods of analysis

Data analysis using an exploratory and descriptive study design was done on the acquired information. An exploratory research strategy was utilized to carry out the patts selection (Pangriya, 2015) and a descriptive research design was used to ensure the orderly progression of all research activities by gathering data on various intermediaries (Chhabra, 2018). With the aid of the appropriate statistical program SPSSv26.0, the acquired data was categorized and examined.

Price spread

Farmers, contractors, wholesalers, processors, retailers and consumers were just a few of the numerous parties involved in the Lavender value chain who provided pertinent information and facts. The price spread—the distinction between the retail price a consumer pays and the price a grower receives—was determined by analysing the marketing of Lavender goods. The revenues produced by various middlemen engaged in the transfer of commodities from the place of production to the end customer were meticulously recorded.

Marketing margin

The following formula is used to determine the marketing margin for a given commodity, which is defined as the difference between the price at which it was purchased and the price at which it was sold through its marketing channels:

$$MM_i = P_{mi} - (P_p + M_{ci})$$

Where,

MM_i : Marketing margins of the i^{th} middleman; P_{mi} : The selling price of the i^{th} middleman; P_p : Purchasing price; M_{ci} : Marketing cost of the i^{th} middleman

Farmer's share in consumer's rupee

This shows the proportion of the retail price that the farmer receives as his or her net price for the produce. The farmer's share of the consumer rupee was calculated using the methodology below.

$$F_s = (F_p / C_p) \times 100$$

Where,

F_s : Farmer's share in consumer's rupee (percentage); F_p : Price received by the farmer (₹/unit); C_p : Price paid by the consumer (₹/unit)

Marketing efficiency

The measures often used encompass the conventional output-to-input ratio (conventional approach), Shepherd's ratio, which contrasts the price of marketed goods with marketing expenses (Shepherd, 2003) and Acharya's modified formula for marketing efficiency (Acharya and Agarwal, 2014).

Conventional method

$$ME = (C_p - F_p) / M_c$$

Where,

ME : Marketing Efficiency; C_p : Price paid by the consumer (₹/unit); F_p : Price received by the farmer (₹/unit); M_c : Total marketing cost

Shepherd's approach

$$ME = C_p / M_c$$

Where,

ME : Marketing Efficiency; C_p : Price paid by the consumer (₹/unit); M_c : Total marketing cost

Acharya's approach

$$ME = C_p / (M_c + MM)$$

Where,

ME: Marketing Efficiency; C_p : Price paid by the consumer (₹/unit); M_c : Total marketing cost;

MM: Total marketing margin

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Lavender value chain map of the Tehri Garhwal district

According to Lundy *et al.*, (2014), a value chain map is a possible place to start when incorporating producers/farmers, traders, consumers and other chain players. As a result, we begin by mapping the Lavender value chain in the research area before presenting our findings (Figure 1). Since conditions for Lavender cultivation, processing and selling are essentially the same across the country, the chain map depicted in Figure 1 can likewise be used for the entire country. The entire value chain is represented on the map, together with its various actors, functions and service providers.

Fig. 1: Overall traditional value chain of Lavender in Tehri Garhwal district

Main actors in Lavender value chain

A person or organization directly engaged in Lavender value chain operations from the stages of production to consumption is considered one of the chain's primary participants. The following are the key participants in the Tehri Garhwal district's Lavender value chain:

Input suppliers: Figure 1 illustrates that the government is the primary source of seeds and planting material (rooted plants), which are used as inputs in the Lavender value chain in the Tehri Garhwal district. Most farmers reuse seeds and plants with roots that they have saved from past harvests. The results are in accordance with the research by **Kostka and Scharrer (2011)** and **Gebremedhnet al. (2019)** on the sesame value chain. On the other hand, farmers hardly ever utilize manures from their own farms to grow Lavender.

The co-operatives offer credit, one of the key inputs needed by Lavender producers. Contractors are a further alternate source of credit, followed by banks and money lenders.

Farmers/ Producers

The majority of Lavender producers in the study region are small-scale farmers. The majority of farmers still practice traditional farming methods, including monoculture. They sow rooted plants and then perform all manual cultural tasks necessary for cultivation after that. They solely grow Lavender for commercial use. They provide the contractors with their produce.

Contractors (C)

The majority of the contractors were between the ages of 41 and 50, with 50% holding diplomas and graduate degrees, respectively. Twenty percent of contractors work exclusively in commerce, twenty percent in trade with agriculture and twenty percent in trade with related activities make up the remainder of the workforce. The processors receive the harvested Lavender yield from them. They do sell straight to stores in some instances.

Processor (PR)

The majority of the processors had a diploma as their primary education and were in their 30s or 30s. The market acceptance of Lavender products is being hampered by the processors problems with lack of consumer understanding regarding consumption habits, small scale, low capacity units, low promotional and presentation of produce, etc. They give the processors the harvested Lavender yield. They offer the wholesalers the harvested Lavender supply.

Wholesalers (WH)

The bulk of wholesalers are well educated and involved in business ownership. They market the gathered Lavender products to shops.

Retailers (RT)

Most of the merchants (retailers) were well educated and between the ages of 31 and 40. Retail trade and trade combined with agriculture were the only activities of the sample stores. Through direct purchases from contractors or wholesalers, they market the harvested lavender products to consumers directly.

Lavender market channel

The individuals, groups and activities required to move ownership of commodities from the site of production to the point of consumption are referred to as a marketing channel. It is also referred to as a distribution channel because it is how items reach the consumer, the end user. In the Tehri Garhwal district, there are two primary marketing outlets for Lavender sales. These are:

Channel I Farmers – Contractor – Processor – Wholesaler – Retailer – Consumer

Channel II Farmers – Contractor – Retailer – Consumer

The field investigation revealed that contractors in the area had the best chance of buying Lavender straight from local producers. A buy-back program/ policy required the tested farmers to sell all of their crops to contractors.

Table 1: Price structure and cost analysis of value chain I and value chain II of Lavender

Actors	Price Structure and Cost Drivers (₹/kg)												
	Activities	Value Chain I						Value Chain II					
		Pre-pandemic		During-pandemic		Post-pandemic		Pre-pandemic		During-pandemic		Post-pandemic	
		Bulb	%	Bulb	%	Bulb	%	Bulb	%	Bulb	%	Bulb	%
Producer	Sale price	297.00	6.00	518.00	5.67	1140.00	6.31	347.00	13.51	568.00	13.07	1700.00	9.86
Contactor	Purchase price	297.00	6.00	518.00	5.67	1140.00	6.31	347.00	13.51	568.00	13.07	1700.00	9.86
	Sorting/ grading	14.50	0.29	15.75	0.17	20.00	0.11	14.50	0.56	15.75	0.36	20.00	0.12
	Transport cost	7.50	0.15	8.25	0.09	11.15	0.06	7.50	0.29	8.25	0.19	11.15	0.06
	Spoilage loss	32.75	0.66	44.25	0.48	42.00	0.23	33.75	1.31	44.25	1.02	45.00	0.26
	Marketing cost	7.50	0.15	7.25	0.08	7.00	0.04	6.25	0.24	8.00	0.18	8.25	0.05
	Miscellaneous Expenses	11.00	0.22	18.00	0.20	32.15	0.18	15.75	0.61	32.00	0.74	39.10	0.23
	Margin	230.10	4.65	293.19	3.21	791.00	4.38	1381.75	53.81	1980.00	45.57	7131.75	41.37
	Sale price	534.60	10.80	818.44	8.96	1938.00	10.73	1735.00	67.57	2556.00	58.82	8840.00	51.28
Processor	Purchase price	534.60	10.80	818.44	8.96	1938.00	10.73	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Transport cost	11.75	0.24	23.20	0.25	27.00	0.15	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Weighing charges	1.50	0.03	1.75	0.02	1.90	0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Spoilage loss	27.75	0.56	52.27	0.57	39.00	0.22	-	-	-	-	-	-

	Distillation charges	220.00	4.44	470.00	5.15	280.25	1.55	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Labour	8.00	0.16	13.25	0.15	11.75	0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Marketing cost	7.25	0.15	8.25	0.09	11.00	0.06	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Miscellaneous Expenses	35.30	0.71	194.00	2.12	310.25	1.72	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Margin	1703.47	34.41	2856.29	31.27	6190.60	34.26	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Sale price	2245.32	45.35	3682.98	40.32	8139.60	45.05	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wholesaler	Purchase price	2245.32	45.35	3682.98	40.32	8139.60	45.05	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Transport cost	10.23	0.21	23.95	0.26	34.00	0.19	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Spoilage loss	22.00	0.44	89.25	0.98	36.25	0.20	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Marketing cost	17.00	0.34	19.00	0.21	20.50	0.11	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Miscellaneous Expenses	38.70	0.78	48.25	0.53	66.25	0.37	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Margin	1105.66	22.33	2006.64	21.97	4049.30	22.41	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Sale price	3367.98	68.03	5708.62	62.50	12209.40	67.57	-	-	-	-	-	-
Retailer	Purchase price	3367.98	68.03	5708.62	62.50	12209.40	67.57	1735.00	67.57	2556.00	58.82	8840.00	51.28
	Transport cost	13.00	0.26	32.00	0.35	19.24	0.11	13.00	0.51	15.75	0.36	19.50	0.11
	Spoilage loss	18.25	0.37	17.15	0.19	25.26	0.14	23.25	0.91	38.00	0.87	31.25	0.18
	Marketing cost	20.70	0.42	24.50	0.27	32.75	0.18	25.75	1.00	37.50	0.86	34.75	0.20
	Miscellaneous Expenses	7.00	0.14	14.75	0.16	25.26	0.14	9.25	0.36	45.75	1.05	44.15	0.26
	Margin	1562.25	31.55	3400.67	37.23	5827.76	32.25	807.05	31.43	1751.70	40.31	8363.25	48.52

	Sale price	4950.93	100.00	9133.79	100.00	18069.91	100.00	2567.80	100.00	4345.20	100.00	17238.00	100.00
Consumer Price		4950.93	100.00	9133.79	100.00	18069.91	100.00	2567.80	100.00	4345.20	100.00	17238.00	100.00
Price Spread		4653.93	94.00	8615.79	94.33	16929.91	93.69	2220.80	86.49	3777.20	86.93	15538.00	90.14

Source: Researcher's calculation on the basis of primary data

Price spread

Value chain I has a high price spread and as the number of intermediaries increases, the price spread also grows. This explains why there is difference throughout the channels (Table 1).

4.1.9.1.2 Cost drivers along the Lavender value chain

The retailer has a higher cost for marketing Lavender in both chains, according to calculations of cost drivers of actors in the Lavender value chain in the Tehri Garhwal district. But when compared, the total marketing expenses incurred by both chains, value chain II has the lowest marketing expenses because there are fewer market intermediaries (Figure 2).

Fig.2: Marketing cost drivers of Lavender

Source: Researcher's calculation on the basis of primary data

Marketing margins

Processors in value chain I during pre- and post-pandemic received the highest profit, followed by retailers during the pandemic, according to assessments of the marketing margins of actors in the Tehri Garhwal district's Lavender value chain. Retailer receives the highest margin in value chain II as compared to the contractor (Figure 3). The overall margin was highest in post-pandemic due to awareness and health benefit to the consumers followed by during-pandemic in both the value chains.

Fig. 3: Margin of Lavender

Source: Researcher’s calculation on the basis of primary data

4.1.9.1.4 Farmer’s share in consumer’s rupee

Another important factor in channel efficiency is the farmer's portion of the consumer's rupee. Due to the significant marketing expenses incurred by the intermediaries, it can be inferred from the Figure 4 that the farmer's share of the consumer's rupee was relatively large in value chain II as compared to value chain I. The final results showed that farmers may greatly raise their share of the rupee paid by the end user by doing away with one or more middlemen and cutting down on marketing costs.

Fig. 4: Farmer’s share in consumer’s rupee of Lavender

Source: Researcher's calculation on the basis of primary data

4.1.9.1.5 Marketing efficiency

The analysis utilizing Acharya's method (Figure 5) showed that the marketing effectiveness in value chain II was highest in the pre-pandemic period, followed by during- and post-pandemic periods. If we compare the two value chains' overall marketing effectiveness, value chain II, which was sold through fewer intermediaries, was far more effective than value chain I.

Fig. 5: Marketing efficiency of Lavender using Acharya's, Conventional and Shepherd's approach

Source: Researcher's calculation on the basis of primary data

In the conventional method, value chain I was more efficient for Lavender bulbs at pre- and during-pandemic. While, it was more efficient in value chain II at post-pandemic (Figure 5).

The Figure 5 showed that, in accordance with Shepherd's approach, marketing efficiency was higher in value chains I at pre- and during- pandemic and at post-pandemic value chain II was more efficient.

Conclusion:

According to the current study's findings, the Tehri Garhwal district has a number of players involved in the Lavender value chain. Farmers, contractors, processors, wholesalers, retailers, and consumers make up the majority of the market. The prices farmers receive are lower than

those received by other middlemen. As a result, there is a demand for Lavender that is of a higher quality, which might be achieved by utilizing numerous current farming techniques and technology. These procedures can improve both the product's quality and its availability to the export market. When it comes to marketing margins, the processors and merchants often benefit the most in both the pre-, during- and post-pandemic value chains for Lavender. This shows that the Lavender market is underdeveloped and that everyone involved might add value and increase their profits with a few minor adjustments to agricultural methods and the application of contemporary technology.

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